

Quantum Particle in a Box and Entropy Extermization

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 7, 2019

In (1), a quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls is described in terms of a p (momentum) distribution involving all p 's from minus infinite to infinite. The spatial wavefunction which is roughly of the form $\sin(kx)$ involves k which is the root mean square momentum. The energy E is an average energy which satisfies $\int dp p^2/2m f_p^2$ in one dimension. The condition of a zero wavefunction at the walls is also enforced. Here f_p is the Fourier transform of $W(x)$, the wavefunction, and is of the form $\cos(ap - \pi/2 n) / (E - p^2/2m)$ or $\sin(ap - \pi/2 n) / (E - p^2/2m)$, where n is the energy level (1). In this note, we point out that f_p may be obtained from a variational principle which uses $W(a)=0$ as a constraint. Next, we argue that there may somehow be a temperature in the wall which forces an average energy of E_{ave} . Normally, one would treat such a system as a Fermi-Dirac gas or Bose-Einstein gas. Recently, however, (2), it has been suggested one may extremize Shannon's spatial entropy to treat such a system. Here we extremize Shannon's momentum entropy with the $W(a)=0$ constraint incorporated and compare with the case of (2).

Quantum Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

In (1) and (3), it is argued that f_p , the Fourier transform of the wavefunction $W(x)$ of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls is given by:

$$f_p = C n^n \sin(ap - \pi/2 n) / (E - p^2/2m) \text{ where } E = 6.28n/L \text{ and } n \text{ is the energy level} \quad ((1))$$

Here the center of the box is at $x=0$ and so one has $\sin(ap)$, then $\cos(ap)$, etc as n changes. It seems ((1)) is of the form of a solution of a variational principle, namely one extremizes $W(a)$ subject to the constraint that $\int dp (E - p^2/2m) = 0$. If $f_p = f - p$ one uses $W(a) = \sum_{p>0} f_p \cos(ap)^2$, and if $f_p = -f - p$ $W(a) = \sum_{p>0} f_p \sin(ap)^2$. Thus, one extremizes:

$$f_p [\cos(ap) \text{ or } \sin(ap)] + b f_p^2 (E - p^2/2m) \quad ((2))$$

to obtain an expression of the form of ((1)). It may be noted that $W(a)=0$ and $\int dp f_p^2 (E - p^2/2m) = 0$ as well.

At first, this extremization may appear to be a curiosity as it does not apply to other quantum mechanical situations. In fact, $W(a)=0$ at the box walls is a special case. Often, bound wavefunctions extend to infinite, although they are strongly damped. It seems, however, that this constraint may be useful in evaluating the gas of "hot" particles in a box with an infinite potential at the walls.

Hot Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

In general, one treats single particle states with a temperature in the following way:

$$\text{density}(x) = \sum_n W_n(x) W_n(x) \exp(-E_n/T) \quad ((3))$$

Here n is the energy level and $W_n(x)$ the n th wavefunction. For multiparticles, $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ may be replaced with a determinant, but the general idea from classical statistical mechanics is used. In some cases, $W_n(x)$ might be obtained from a Schrodinger equation with a potential based on the single particle wavefunctions of the "other particles", such as in the case of a nucleus. The, $W_n(x,T)$ states can be used by using a temperature dependent Hartree Fock approach. Here, we wish to investigate maximizing Shannon's momentum entropy, incorporating $W(a)=0$ as a constraint, as a number of people in the literature are using single particle Shannon's entropies to derive new Schrodinger type equations incorporating entropy. It seems the Fermi gas approach has been used for decades and one would assume it matches experiment. It is not clear if the approach of maximizing momentum entropy matches experiment.

For the sake of argument, consider extremizing:

$$\sum_p (-1)^{fp} \ln[fp] + b_1 \exp(ipa) + b_2 (E - p^2/2m) fp + b_3 fp \quad ((4))$$

Here b_1 , b_2 and b_3 are Lagrange multipliers and we explicitly include $W(a)=0$ as a constraint. E is Eave of the hot temperature system. Then:

$$-4 \ln(fp) - 2fp + b_1 [\cos(pa) \text{ or } \sin(pa)] + b_3 2 fp + b_2 (E - p^2/2m) fp = 0 \quad ((5))$$

This equation can be solved numerically for fp . With fp , one has $W(x) = \sum_p fp \exp(ipx)$. Note: $\cos(pa)$ or $\sin(pa)$ can be used depending on whether $fp=f-p$ or $fp=-f-p$. One may note this result would be very similar to a classical Boltzmann solution $\exp(-ap^2/2m)$ if it were not for the constraint term $\cos(pa)$ or $\sin(pa)$. An fp of the form $\exp(-ap^2/2m)$ leads to a wavefunction $W(x)$ of the form $\exp(-bx^2)$ which represents the ground state of a quantum oscillator. The oscillator wavefunction goes to zero at plus and minus infinite, but the density would be the central region. For a Fermi gas, the density is throughout the system.

Comparison with the Literature

In (2), the authors extremize Shannon's single particle spatial entropy - $\int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)W(x)]$ subject to a constraint on energy to obtain a general Schrodinger like equation. They then apply this to various cases, including the particle in a box with an infinite potential. Their equation is:

- $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + T W(x) \ln [W(x)W(x)] = h W(x)$ where h is a constant and T temperature ((5))

They apply the boundary condition $W(0) = W(1) = 0$ to account for the wavefunction disappearing at the boundary.

It should be noted a solution of ((5)) is $\exp(-ax^2)$, the ground state of a quantum oscillator. In such a case, the walls would need to be placed at minus and plus infinite. This is in fact, similar to the momentum Shannon's entropy case discussed above except for the inclusion of $W(a)=0$ as a constraint which leads to an extra term in the momentum equation.

It is surprising perhaps that a hot particle (at temperature T) in a box with walls at plus and minus infinite would concentrate in the center of the box, which is what the ground state oscillator result seems to show.

If one wanted to incorporate $W(a)=0$ as a constraint, it seems one might extremize:

$-W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)W(x)] + b_1 W(x)W(x) + b_2 W(x) \delta(x-a) + b_3 [(-1/2m) (W \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W - Eave)]$. ((6))

This would give a somewhat different result than that of ((2)), where the boundary condition has been included in the quantity being extremized.

Momentum Versus Spatial Entropy

It is interesting to note that extremizing momentum versus spatial Shannon's entropy may lead to similar results. In classical statistical mechanics, one maximizes momentum entropy or analyses two particle elastic collisions at a point in space. This leads to $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ whether or not a potential $V(x)$ is present. One then shows $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ is consistent with the momentum case. One does not have to extremize both momentum and spatial entropy together. Momentum entropy results affect the spatial entropy case. It seems that a similar situation may exist in quantum mechanics as f_p and $W(x)$ are directly linked through the Fourier transform.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that given that all possible momentum states p contribute to each resonance wavefunction for a quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential at the wall (according to (1) and (3)), then one should be able to maximize Shannon's entropy for momentum $-f_p^2 \ln[f_p^2]$ subject to an energy constraint and normalization as well as to a constraint of $W(a)=0$ written as $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) = 0$. It seems incorporating $W(a)=0$ as a constraint leads to a different result from that presented in the literature (2). We also note that the result in the literature, as well as the Shannon's momentum extremization without the $W(a)=0$ as a constraint, both lead to $\exp(-ax^2)$ type spatial wavefunctions (as a solution). This

represents the walls being at plus and minus infinite, but also represent the ground state of a quantum oscillator. The hot particle would then be concentrated in the central region which is unusual and very different from the results of a Fermi gas.

References

1. Majernik, V and Majernikova, E. The Momentum Entropy of the Infinite Well (Journal of Physics General Physics 1999)
file:///home/chronos/u-8dd8a372933f68c28035cee18f7c4c1f27fe9a76/Downloads/diplomka.pdf <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230930491>
2. Jacobsen, P and Lychagin, V. Maximum Entropy Wavefunctions (2006)
<http://www.math.uit.no/seminar/Preprints/06-06-PJVL.pdf>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box